

STRATEGIES FOR ENHANCING STUDENTS' PRACTICAL SKILLS IN ELECTRICAL INSTALLATION AND MAINTENANCE WORKS IN TECHNICAL COLLEGES IN ENUGU STATE

Nnobulu, Onyinye Gift, Prof. Alio A. N and Dr. Ugwuode A.A

Department Of Technology and Vocational Education Enugu State University of Science and Technology,
ESUT

Email: abygalio@yahoo.com; adaora.ugwuode@esut.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12187030>

Abstract: The central purpose of this study was to determine the strategies for enhancing the students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population for the study comprised 44 Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works (EIMW) teachers in five technical colleges in Enugu State. The entire population was used, therefore no sampling due to the manageable size of the population. The instrument for data collection was a 22-item structured questionnaire divided in two sub-categories based on the research questions that guided the study. The questionnaire items were structured in four-point rating scale. The questionnaire was validated by three experts, two from Department of Technology and Vocational Education and one from Department of Mathematics and Computer Education in Enugu State University of Science and Technology, while the reliability of the instrument yielded 0.76 using Cronbach Alpha. Out of 44 copies of the questionnaire distributed, 41 copies were properly filled and returned giving 93.81% return rate. The data collected were analyzed using mean, standard deviation and t-test statistics. Based on the result of data analysis, the study identified the pedagogical and facilities strategies for enhancing students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State. Following the findings, recommendations were made among which include; Installation and Maintenance Works (EIMW) teachers should adopt pedagogical strategies that will enhance the delivery of practical skill training to the students in technical colleges and teachers should be properly monitored on the use of pedagogical strategies that will enhance the practical skill training of Installation and Maintenance Works (EIMW) students in technical colleges.

Keywords: Practical Skills, Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works and Technical Colleges

Introduction

The contemporary Nigeria society is facing low quality of education and unemployment among the youths. Education has gained such an unpredicted prominence the world over, that many nations of the world see the level of education attainment or achievement of the citizenry as factor for measuring all aspects of National development. Onyebuenyi, Mbah and Odeluga (2017) stated that education and training is the medium for acquisition of minimum ethical standards that can propel its recipients towards the development of oneself for maximum benefit. It is imperative to note that education is provided for the development of practical skills and competencies for different occupational task. Years of negligence and unfavorable political climate in education

have led to the learner's unemployment, low acquisition of practical skills and under-utilization of skills to yield maximum economic benefits.

It is believed that acquisition of practical skills for self-employment is one of the key solutions to addressing the imbalance in the quality of education. Practical skills are the manipulative psychomotor abilities used in the performance of task. According to Mbah and Umurhurhu (2016), skill is the ability to make purposeful movements that are necessary to complete and master a particular task. Practical skills possessed are demonstrated through the habit of acting, thinking and behaving in a specific way such that the activities becomes natural through repetition of practice. Olaitan (2014) opined that practical skills determine the rate of self-employed human resources and should be given priority for creating a prosperous and competitive economy. Okafor (2017) stated that the quality of the educational system of a country is the main factor determining labour quality and self-employment. It therefore becomes imperative that students in technical colleges should be exposed to different practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance work to enable them acquire knowledge and manipulative skills for employment in electrical industry.

Technical colleges are post primary education system designed to train craftsmen and master craftsmen in different vocational/career areas with specific emphasis in practical skills training. According to Okolie, Igwe and Elom (2019) technical college programmes are aimed at training intermediate workforce with relevant skills for employment in areas that human, machines, control techniques and materials are used. Technical colleges admit upper basic education leavers and provide them with full vocational courses for three years in different career choice.

Furthermore, the curriculum of technical college programmes focuses on crafts in engineering trades, technical skills and vocational skill development for paid and self-employment. However, the quality of academic programmes in technical colleges is regulated by National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) through curriculum development, supervision and periodic accreditation visits while the National Business and Technical Examinations Board (NABTEB) is responsible for the examination and certification of the occupational trades leading to the award of National Technical Certificate (NTC) and Advance National Technical Certificate (ANTC) as contained in NBTE (2011). The trades offered in the Technical Colleges in Nigeria according to Federal Government of Nigeria (2013) include: Building Trades; Beauty Culture Trades, Computer Craft Practice, Bricklaying, Carpentry, Plumbing, Motor Vehicle Repair and Maintenance Works, Radio and Television Maintenance Works, Welding and Fabrication, Home Economics Work, Wood Trades, Printing Work, Textile Work, Hospitality and Mechanical Engineering Work, Agricultural Implement Craft Trade, Auto Electric Works, Vehicle Body Building Works and Motor Vehicle Mechanic's Works, Refrigeration and Air Conditioning Works, Radio, TV and Electronic works, Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works among others.

Electrical installation and maintenance work is a trade offered in technical colleges to prepare individual with job-satisfying requirements towards employment and self-reliance. Electrical installation and maintenance work according to Ogwa (2015) provides technical training to recipients in order to meet the demands of electrical installation in domestic and industrial as well as allowing the students to identify their career objectives. Practical skills training in electrical installation and maintenance works are needed to develop manipulative skills and dexterity in electrical installation and maintenance job task and making students confident and self-

reliant (Odika and Tom, 2020). Electrical installation and maintenance works curriculum is designed to prepare the students to acquire entry level knowledge and manipulative skills for employment in the electrical industry. Students who undergo training in electrical installation and maintenance trades are expected to get hold of practical skills for fineness in installation of electrical machines and equipment, maintenance of machines and equipment, winding of electrical machines, testing and inspection of electrical installations, repair of electrical machine and others. The teachers of electrical installation and maintenance work are expected to consider the most effective strategies that will enable them to achieve the instructional objective and therefore, practical skill development of the students.

Moreover, a teacher of Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work (EIMW) is the one who gives instructions and communicates knowledge, skills and attitudes to EIMW students. The teacher acts as the conduit through which knowledge and practical skills of EIMW could be transmitted as such he should use appropriate teaching and supervisory strategies together with learning resources to enhance performance of students in practical skills through activity-based instruction where students are given opportunities to be more active in the class (Tumba and Shuaibu, 2016). The teachers, curriculum planners etc in technical education need to adopt strategies that would enhance student's performance in practical skills.

Strategies in teaching EIMW can be seen as a way or process of making the teaching more productive in meeting the learners' needs. Eze (2016) defined strategies as ways or measures that needs the commitment of the teacher and curriculum planners in achieving the desired result practical skill development. Also, enhancing is improving or making-up when something is not up to the expected standard, Therefore, to enhance students' practical skills in technical colleges, there are strategies to consider in order to achieve the desired result and they include pedagogical strategies, facilities strategies and administrative strategies. In the context of this study, the researcher considered the pedagogical and facilities strategies to enhancing the students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State.

The pedagogical strategies focus on the instructional delivery and methodology in teaching and learning of EIMW in technical colleges. Teachers of EIMW are expected to plan their lesson properly by carefully choosing the objectives of the lesson, devising on making the learners participate in the learning process in a more responsible way, selecting the appropriate teaching methods, appropriate strategies for learners' feedback as well as determining the appropriate assessment procedure. The aim is to achieve the performance of students in practical skills. Okafor (2019) opined that pedagogical strategies are based on the teacher's ability to adopt the relevant teaching skills in order to improve the teaching and learning processes using available instructional facilities. The pedagogical strategies for enhancing the students' practical skills could also be linked to Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES). Ojokuku, Emeahara, Aboyade and Chris (2015) pointed out that SIWES is designed to improve the student's practical skills through partnership with relevant industries and real work. The pedagogical strategies may not give the desired result if the instructional facilities are not available and utilized for students' skill acquisition in EIMW.

The instructional facilities used in teaching of EIMW affect the acquisition of practical skills by the students. Instructional facilities in 21st century workshops are expected to have information and Communication Technology (ICT) components for digital skill training. The facilities strategies cover the workshop facilities, classrooms, ICT facilities and other resources provided to aid the effective implementation of the EIMW

curriculum in technical colleges. Ikeora (2020) opined that technical college instructional delivery depends on the facilities strategies adopted in the requisition and procurement for the implementation of the programmes. Facilities in teaching could be defined as a place, amenity or piece of equipment provided for the purpose of teaching and learning exercise. The facility strategies cover the various ways of ensuring that facilities for teaching and learning are utilized properly and effectively.

Every technical college administrators and teachers need to develop effective strategies in order to improve students' practical skills. Akamobi (2017) depicted that enhancing the students' performance in technical colleges for service delivery, demands quality of pedagogical instruction and facilities that would control other factors to change attitude, knowledge, idea and impact the desired practical skills in the students. This is important because achieving sustainable development goal depends on the level of education and practical skill of the learners with the state-of-the-art facilities. The EIMW teachers in technical colleges would be used for the study as their experience will help in identifying the strategies for enhancing the students' in practical skills. Teachers experience according to Mbah and Odike (2021) affect adoption of innovations and pedagogical strategies in teaching as less experience teachers utilize modern innovative approaches more than the more experience teachers following their age of services. The identification of these strategies is pertinent to the study as technological and economic development are equally affected by the impact created by poor performance of students in practical skills. Hence, this research work aims at determining the strategies for enhancing the students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State.

Statement of the Problem

The development of adequate skills and competencies is an important characteristic of electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges. The instructional activities need to be centered on the students for them to gain maximum practical skills for self-development and fulfillment in the labour market. The achievement of these is dependent on the quality of strategies adopted in enhancing the students' academic performance. Regrettably, due to some barriers, the level of students' performance in practical skills when compared with the demands of the labour market and technological advancement is nothing to talk about. This explains why most employers of labour in this nation believe that the products of electrical installation and maintenance works from technical colleges do not have basic work skills in their occupational field (Akamobi, 2017). It is imperative to note that the students' practical skills is not commensurate with the objective of electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges and therefore calls for identifying effective strategies to address these conditions.

There is low practical skill of the graduates of electrical installation and maintenance works from technical colleges as observed by Akamobi (2017). This condition needs to be addressed by identifying the strategies that need to be adopted in the teaching of electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges. These poor practical skills has negative consequences on the employability of these students, quality of education, societal contributions and development of technological idea in modern world. This situation needs to be addressed by identifying the strategies for enhancing the performance of students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the strategies for enhancing the students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State. Specifically, the study sought to determine the;

- ❖ Pedagogical strategies for enhancing students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State.
- ❖ Facility strategies for enhancing students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

- What are the pedagogical strategies for enhancing students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State?
- What are the facility strategies for enhancing students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State?

Hypotheses

Two null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁ There is no significant difference between the mean scores of experience and less experience teachers on the pedagogical strategies for enhancing the students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State.

H₀₂ There is no significant difference between the mean scores of experience and less experience teachers on the facilities strategies for enhancing the students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State.

Method

A survey research design was adopted for the study. Nworgu (2015) defined survey research design as one in which a group of people or items are studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few of them within the entire group. The study adopted this design due to the polychotomous instrument used and the teacher's opinions which were sought. The area for the study was Enugu State of Nigeria. Enugu State is located in Igboland and is one of the five States in South-East geopolitical zone of Nigeria. The population for the study comprises 44 teachers of electrical installation and maintenance works in 33 technical colleges in Enugu State. The population was determined based on the field survey conducted by the researcher. The number was manageable and as such, there was no sampling.

The data was collected using 22-item structured questionnaire developed by the researcher based on the review of related literature. The instrument was structured in four-point response scales; Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD) with a normal value of 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. The validation of the instrument was done using three experts, two from Department of Technology and Vocational Education and one from Department of Mathematics and Computer Education, all from Enugu State University of Science and Technology. Afterwards, their corrections and suggestions were used to prepare the final instrument used for the study. The instrument was trial tested using 10 copies on EIMW teachers in Anambra State who were not in the area of the study. The reliability coefficient yielded 0.76 using Crombach Alpha method. This 0.76 coefficient is in-line with Uzoagulu (2013) that reliability index of 0.60 to 1 shows that the instrument could be used for the data collection.

The administration of the questionnaire was carried out using two research assistants and out of 44 copies distributed 41 copies were returned giving 93.18% return rate. Weighted means and standard deviations were

used to answer the research questions. Decisions on the research questions were made using the lower and upper limits of the mean based on a four-point scale. The standard deviation was used to determine the homogeneity or otherwise of the opinions of the respondents. The t-test was used to test the null hypotheses. The analysis was carried out using Statistical Packages Social Science (SPSS) version 25. The significant value (at 2-tail) was compared with .05 level of significant at the appropriate degree of freedom. The null hypothesis was not significant when the significant value was less than .05 level of significance and at appropriate degree of freedom; otherwise the null hypothesis was significant.

Results

The results of the study obtained were presented in Tables based on the research questions and hypotheses that guided the study (see table 1-4).

Research Question 1

What are the pedagogical strategies for enhancing the students’ practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State?

Table 1:

Mean scores and standard deviation of the respondents on the pedagogical strategies for enhancing the students’ practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State

S/N	Pedagogical strategies for enhancing the students’ practical skills in EIMW includes:	Highly Experience d N= 29		Less Experience N= 12		Overall		Decision
		X ₁	SD ₁	X ₂	SD ₂	X _G	SD _G	
1	Addressing the individual differences among the learners based on their learning abilities.	3.0	0.8	3.0	0.8	3.0	0.8	Agree
2	Introducing blended learning approach in practical skill works	3.3	0.6	3.3	0.6	3.3	0.6	Agree
3	Partnering with relevant industrial workshop for practical skill training	3.3	0.6	3.3	0.6	3.3	0.6	Agree
4	Adopting teamwork in areas of difficulties	3.3	0.6	3.3	0.6	3.3	0.6	Agree
5	Utilizing relevant instructional aids in teaching EIMW	3.3	0.7	3.3	0.7	3.3	0.7	Agree
6	Adopting relevant instructional methods in teaching EIMW	3.3	0.8	3.3	0.8	3.3	0.8	Agree
7	Taking the students on field trip in real world of practical	2.8	0.7	2.8	0.7	2.8	0.7	Agree
8	Adopting effective workshop facilities management in teaching EIMW	2.8	0.7	2.8	0.7	2.8	0.7	Agree
9	Using modern/innovative teaching approaches in EIMW	3.0	0.8	2.9	0.7	2.9	0.8	Agree
10	Proper assessment of EIMW instruction	3.0	0.7	3.0	0.7	3.0	0.7	Agree
11	Using interactive teaching approaches in EIMW instruction	2.9	0.6	2.9	0.6	2.9	0.6	Agree
12	Maintaining a conducive learning environment	2.8	0.8	2.8	0.7	2.8	0.8	Agree
Cluster Mean/SD		3.12	0.74	3.10	0.73	3.1	0.7	Agree
						1	3	

Note: X =Mean; SD = Standard Deviation

The result of data analysis presented in Table 1 indicates that the overall item mean scores ranges from 2.87 to 3.36 depicting agree. The items have overall cluster mean of 3.11 and standard deviation of 0.73. The low level of standard deviation of 0.73 obtained indicates that the respondents have consensus opinion in their responses to the items as pedagogical strategies for enhancing the performance of students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of experienced and less experienced teachers on the pedagogical strategies for enhancing the students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State.

Table 2:

Summary of t-test analysis on mean scores of experienced and less experienced teachers on the pedagogical strategies for enhancing the students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State

Variables	N	t	df	Sig. (2tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Decision
Experienced	29	.529	39	.681	.56329	.93878	NS
Less Experienced	12						

The t-test analysis in Table 2 shows that the t-value at 0.05 level of significant and 39 degree of freedom for the 12 items is 0.529 with a significant value of 0.681. Since the significant value of 0.681 is more than the 0.05 level of significance the null hypothesis is not significant. This means that there is no significant difference on the mean scores of experienced and less experienced teachers on the pedagogical strategies for enhancing the students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State.

Research Question 2

What are the facilities strategies for enhancing the students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State?

Table 3:

Mean scores and standard deviation of the respondents on the facilities strategies for enhancing the students’ practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State

S/ N	Facilities strategies for enhancing the students’ practical skills in EIMW includes:	Highly Experienced N= 29		Less Experienced N= 12		Overall		Decision
		X ₁	SD ₁	X ₂	SD ₂	X _G	SD _G	
13	Ensuring the availability of relevant instructional facilities	2.8	0.8	2.8	0.7	2.8	0.8	Agree
14	Provision of classroom spaces with offices for effective teaching	2.8	0.7	2.9	0.6	2.9	0.7	Agree
15	Provision of classroom laboratory for effective practical work training	2.8	0.7	2.9	0.7	2.9	0.7	Agree
16	Adequate maintenance of facilities for effective teaching.	3.3	0.5	3.4	0.5	3.3	0.5	Agree
17	Provision of modern teaching facilities such as computer, internet, software packages etc.	3.0	0.8	3.0	0.8	3.0	0.8	Agree
18	Improving the physical facilities in technical colleges	3.0	0.9	3.1	0.8	3.1	0.9	Agree
19	Provision of electric power for practical skill works.	3.6	0.4	3.5	0.5	3.6	0.4	Strongly Agree
20	Using video conferencing facilities in practical skill demonstration	3.1	0.7	3.2	0.6	3.1	0.7	Agree
21	Replacing obsolete tools with digital age tools	3.2	0.5	3.3	0.4	3.2	0.5	Agree
22	Changing the obsolete equipment in school environment	3.0	0.6	3.0	0.5	3.0	0.6	Agree
	Cluster Mean/SD	3.10	0.72	3.16	0.67	3.1	0.7	Agree

Note: X =Mean; SD = Standard Deviation

The data presented in Table 3 indicates that item 19 had mean score of 3.61 showing strongly agree while the remaining items ranges from 2.87 to 3.39 depicting agree. The items have overall cluster mean of 3.13 and standard deviation of 0.70. The low level of standard deviation of 0.7 obtained indicates that the

respondents have consensus opinion in their responses to the items as the facilities strategies for enhancing the students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of experience and less experience teachers on the facilities strategies for enhancing the students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State.

Table 4:

Summary of t-test analysis on mean scores of experienced and less experienced teachers on the facilities strategies for enhancing the students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State

Variables	N	t	df	Sig. (2tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Decision
Experienced	29	.316	39	.731	.51122	.612873	NS
Less Experienced	12						

The result of t-test analysis in Table 4 shows that the t-value at 0.05 level of significant and 39 degree of freedom for the 10 items is 0.316 with a significant value of 0.731. Since the significant value of 0.731 is more than the 0.05 level of significance the null hypothesis is not significant. This means that there is no significant difference on the mean ratings of experience and less experienced teachers on the facilities strategies for enhancing the students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State.

Major findings of the study

Based on the data analysis, the following major finding were made:

- ❖ Pedagogical strategies for enhancing the performance of student's practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu Stat. a significant difference does not exist on the mean scores teacher on the facilities strategies for enhancing the performance of students practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges based on experience.
- ❖ Facilities strategies for enhancing the performance of student's practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State. The study showed that there is no significant difference on the mean scores of teachers on the facilities strategies for enhancing the performance of student's practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State based on experience.

Discussion of Findings

The result of data analysis according to research question one showed the pedagogical strategies for enhancing students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State. The findings indicated that the pedagogical strategies for enhancing students' practical skills in EIMW in

technical colleges includes; addressing the individual difference among the learners based on their learning abilities, introducing blended learning approach in practical skill works, partnering with relevant industrial workshop for practical skill training, adopting teamwork in areas of difficulty, utilizing relevant instructional aids in teaching EIMW, adopting relevant instructional methods in teaching EIMW, taking the students on field trip in real world of practical, adopting effective workshop facilities management in teaching EIMW, using modern/innovative teaching approaches in EIMW, proper assessment of EIMW instruction, using interactive teaching approaches in EIMW instruction and maintaining a conducive learning environment among others. The implication of the findings of the study was that adopting these strategies in teaching would enhance the students in practical skills. The findings of the study are in consonance with Okafor (2019) which stated that pedagogical strategies depend on the teacher's ability in promoting quality teaching through the teaching skills, use of instructional materials, and teamwork among others. Okafor pointed that teachers should ensure proper utilization of innovative teaching approaches to improve the student's practical skill training.

Furthermore, the findings in null hypotheses one showed that significant difference does not exist between the mean scores of experienced and less experienced teachers on the pedagogical strategies for enhancing the students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State. This implies that experience of the teachers had no influence on the identified pedagogical strategies for enhancing the students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State.

Moreover, the findings of the study in research question two showed the facility strategies for enhancing students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State. Among the facilities strategies identified were ensuring the availability of relevant instructional facilities, provision of classroom spaces with offices, effective teaching, provision of classroom laboratory for effective practical work training, adequate maintenance of facilities for effective teaching, provision of modern teaching facilities such as computer, internet, software packages etc, improving the physical facilities in technical colleges, provision of electric power for practical skill works, using video conferencing facilities in practical skill demonstration, replacing obsolete tools with digital age tools and changing the obsolete equipment in school environment. The findings were in consonance with Ogbodo (2016) and Ikeora (2020) who stated that facilities strategies need to be considered in other to promote quality teaching in all technical education trades subjects. The authors pointed that no meaning instruction and learning will be achieved if facilities needed are not provided by the relevant stakeholders. The study therefore indicates that the identified facility strategies need to be adopted in order to ensure effective practical skill training.

In addition to the above, the findings in the null hypothesis two showed that significant difference does not exist on the mean scores of experienced and less experienced teachers on the facility strategies for enhancing the students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State. This implies that experience of the teachers had no influence on the identified facility strategies for enhancing the students in practical skill in EIMW in technical colleges.

Conclusion

The study identified the strategies for enhancing students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges in Enugu State. The findings showed that government, technical

college administrators and teachers need to adopt the identified pedagogical and facility strategies in order to enhance the students' practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works in technical colleges. These findings would enable the government and administrators of EIMW to ensure that training and re-training programmes are given to the teachers on the pedagogical strategies and facilities should be enhanced to support practical skill training.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

- EIMW teachers should adopt pedagogical strategies that will enhance the delivery of practical skill training to the students in technical colleges.
- The teachers should be properly monitored on the use of pedagogical strategies that will enhance the practical skill training of EIMW students in technical colleges.
- Government and administrators should adopt facility strategies to enable EIMW teachers to enhance practical skill training of students in technical colleges.

REFERENCES

- Akamobi, O. G. (2017). Electrical installation and maintenance practices teachers' assessment of the entrepreneurial skill needs of technical students in Anambra and Enugu State. *M.Sc. Thesis submitted to Department of Vocational Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka.*
- Eze, O. F. (2016). Teachers' perception on the use of computer aided instruction in teaching Business Studies in upper basic education in Orumba South L.G.A of Anambra State. *Unpublished B.Sc. project report presented to Department of Technology and Vocational Education ESUT.*
- Federal Republic of Nigeria. (2013) *National Policy on Education. Lagos: NERDC Press.*
- Ikeora, L.O. (2020). Lecturers' perception of measures for improving teaching-learning of technical education trades courses in technical colleges Anambra State. *unpublished B.Sc. Project Presented to Department of Technology and Vocational Education Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka.*
- Jim, E.U. (2016). Improving business education programme through effective school industry partnership for student's capacity development in River State. *ABEN conference proceedings 3 (1) 149-155.*
- Mbah, C. O. &Odike, F. I. (2021). Influence of ICT innovations in vocational education for achieving sustainable development in Anambra State. Conference paper presented at 3rd international multi-disciplinary conference of Faculty of Education Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University with the theme; education and innovations for sustainable development in Africa 16th to 19th of March, 2021.
- Mbah, C.O. &Umurhurhu, E. B. (2016). Improving the teaching learning of computer aided drafting and designing (CADD) for effective skill development in Nigerian tertiary institution. *International Technology Research Journal (INTERJ) 4(1), 24-29.*

- National Board for Technical Education (2011). *National Diploma (ND) in Mechatronics engineering technology curriculum and course specifications*. Kaduna. [www.nbte.mechatronics engineering technology.com](http://www.nbte.mechatronicsengineeringtechnology.com).
- Nworgu, B.G. (2015). *Educational Research; Basic issues and methodology*. Nsukka; University Trust Publishers.
- Odika, E.M. & Tom, C.C. (2020). Electrical Installation and maintenance work skills for sustainability amongst Graduates of Technical Colleges in River State. *International Journal of Innovation Education Research* 8 (1) 1-10.
- Ogbodo, C.N. (2016). *Strategies for enhancing the teaching of Agricultural science in secondary schools in Omeke Education Zone, of Ebonyi State. Unpublished M. Sc. Dissertation*. Department of Technology and Vocational Education Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu.
- Ogwa, C. E. (2015). Enhancing the use of Instructional Facilities in Technical Colleges for Qualitative Skills Acquisition in Nigeria. *Journal of Information and Knowledge Management*. 5(10) 34-47.
- Ojukuku, B. Y., Emeahara, E. N., Aboyade, M. A. & Chris-Israel, H. O. (2015). *Influence of students Industrial Work Experience Scheme on professional development of library and information science students in South-West, Nigeria. Library Philosophy and Practice (ejournal) 2 (3) 30-43*.
- Okafor, C.E. (2017). *ICT employability skills possessed by business education graduates for sustainable economic empowerment in North West zone of Nigeria. Unpublished Ph.D Thesis*. Department of Technology and Vocational Education. Enugu state university of science and Technology Enugu.
- Okafor, E. C. (2019). Enhancing of employees' motivation on organizational effectiveness in technical colleges in Anambra State. *Journal of management and strategies* 5 (2) 215-228.
- Okolie, U. C., Igwe, P. A. & Elom, E. N. (2019). *Improving graduate outcome for technical colleges in Nigeria. Australian Journal of Career Development* 28(1), 21-30.
- Olaitan, O. O. (2014). Development and Validation of test for assessing students' skills in motor vehicle mechanic work for technical colleges. *Unpublished Ph.D Thesis*, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
- Onyebuanyi, P. N., Mbah, C. O. & Odeluga, P. E. (2017). Enhancing practical skill acquisition among technical college students through information and communication technology for self-reliance in Abia State. *Journal of Vocational Education & Research* 2(1) 252-264

Tumba, I. & Shuaibu, H. (2016). Strategies for improving students' acquisition of practical skills in electrical installation and maintenance works trade in Technical Colleges in Kano State. *International Journal of Engineering and science* 5 (10) 30-40.

Uzoagulu, A. E. (2013). *Practical Guide to Writing Research Project Report in Tertiary Institutions*. Enugu: John Jacobs classic.